

ISic4359

I.Sicily inscription 4359

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2014.09.11

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Bagno Romano? Bufardeci?

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 254

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 386
Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis
inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici
Romani. Berlin. At VIII 686

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